

RESEARCH PAPER

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Biopriming with Beneficial Endophytic and Rhizospheric Soil Actinobacteria on Comparative Growth Promotion and Root Colonization Potentials in Mustard Crop: A Field Appraisal

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Abstract

Mustard is an essential oilseed crop belonging to family Brassicaceae (Cruciferae). In the present study, out of a total of 50 actinobacterial isolates (30 from rhizospheric soil and 20 from endophytic tissues) obtained from mustard plant, two promising isolates (rhizospheric MRS-15 and endophytic MER-33) were evaluated for the plant growth promoting potential and endophytic occurrence in in-vitro assay. The MRS-15 isolate was observed to form biofilm-like structure on root epidermis while MER-33 reached inside the root outer cortex on seed inoculation in mustard seedlings. In the field study, Azotobacter was applied as a reference culture along with the two best isolates (MRS-15 and MER-33). The results revealed significant enhancement of various growth parameters (plant height, fresh and dry shoot and root weight, chlorophyll content) and yield attributes by the two actinobacterial cultures. Whereas seed weight/plant and seed yield were enhanced by all three inoculants over the uninoculated control. The seed quality traits, including the total phenol content and DPPH scavenging activity, were improved by MRS-15 inoculation followed by inoculation with Azotobacter. An increase in viable cell counts of total aerobic bacteria, actinobacteria, and free-living N-fixers was recorded on microbial inoculation as enumerated during different stages of growth. This study accentuates the use of plant growth-promoting actinobacterial isolates for the development of bioinoculant formulation for enhanced growth and seed yield in the mustard crop.

Keywords: Actinobacteria; Endophyte; Plant growth promotion potential; Yield parameters; Biopriming; Mustard

Introduction

Mustard (family Brassicaceae or Cruciferae) is one of the essential oilseed crops grown globally (Mailer, 2016). It is primarily cultivated in Asia followed by America and Europe continents (FAOSTAT, 2024). India is at second and fourth position in area under cultivation and production, respectively (Gangwar and Jain, 2023). Predominant *Brassica* species are cultivated for oil and include Rapeseed (*Brassica napus*) and mustard (*Brassica juncea*). Among these, rapeseed-mustard contributes approximately 28.6% to India's oilseed economy (Shekhawat et al., 2012).

Received:
2025/05/18
Accepted:
2025/06/16
Published:
2025/07/01

Although India occupies second place in mustard production, yet its productivity is far below compared to the world average (Choudhary and Nehra, 2022). Furthermore, mustard responds to nitrogen and phosphate fertilizer as these nutrients function as limiting factors (Sefaoglu et al., 2021). Thus, application of N and P-fertilizers can increase mustard productivity (Rosenberg and Azevedo, 2019). However, considering the escalating prices of nutrient fertilizers and their adverse effects on the soil health including environmental pollution, disruption of natural nutrient cycling, and destruction of beneficial biological communities that otherwise support crop production, there is a need to focus on integrated nutrient management (INM) system and bio-inoculants to improve crop production and soil health (Gupta and Kalhapure, 2024).

Microorganisms play a vital role in agriculture by improving nutrient availability and promoting crop growth owing to their versatile microbial activities (Kalia et al., 2020). Biofertilizers are microbial inoculants that serve a key role in sustainable agronomics, plant tolerance, crop development, recycling of crop residues, and soil fertility, besides serving for the biocontrol of phytopathogens (Kalia and Singh, 2020; Orozco-Mosqueda et al., 2021). Among plant growth-promoting microorganisms (PGPMs), actinobacteria (order Actinomycetales)-Gram-positive, facultative anaerobic bacteria—have gained special attention due to their vital role in host plant development and growth enhancement (Boukhatem and Merabet, 2022). A dynamic relationship exists among various microbial species (bacteria and fungi, including actinobacteria) and the root system of plants. Due to this relationship, plant roots harbour a variety of endophytic actinobacteria (EAct), including *Streptomyces* spp. (50%) and non-*Streptomyces* spp. (Kalia and Singh, 2020). Both endophytic and rhizospheric actinobacteria improve plant health by synthesizing a vast range of bioactive metabolites and bio-functional compounds (Anand et al., 2023). Further, actinobacteria produce an array of extracellular hydrolytic enzymes that can break down complex compounds into valuable nutrients (Selim, 2021).

The actinobacterial genera have enticed renewed interest due to their versatile plant interactions particularly the endophytic occurrence, nutrient-provision roles, and secretion of metabolites that modulate plant immunity, the present research aimed to isolate and characterize rhizospheric and endophytic actinobacterial cultures from mustard plant tissues and rhizospheric soil samples. Additionally, their interaction with the mustard plant was evaluated under *in vitro* and field conditions. This is the first study that comparatively evaluates the effect of seed inoculation using rhizospheric and endophytic actinobacterial isolates vis-à-vis the popular PGPR *Azotobacter* sp. in three different mustard varieties.

Material and methods

Sample collection, isolation and screening of actinomycetes cultures

Thirty rhizospheric and twenty endophytic actinobacteria were isolated from mustard plant soil and tissues collected across Punjab. Both soil (10 g) and plant segments (1.0 cm) were serially diluted and plated on actinobacteria agar (Kaur, 2024), incubated at $28\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ for 7–10 days, and CFU/g was recorded.

Effect of inoculation of endophytic actinobacterial cultures and *Azotobacter* on mustard seeds under lab conditions

Mustard seeds were surface sterilized and inoculated with 48 hours old broth cultures ($9.1 \log \text{cfu mL}^{-1}$) of MRS-15, MER-33 and *Azotobacter* cultures and uninoculated liquid broth as control. The treated seeds were incubated on sterile, moistened Whatman paper at $28\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ for one week. The root cap region (1–2 cm) of germinated seeds were stained with congo-red (1.0% w/v), washed thoroughly with water, and then visualized microscopically for bacterial-root association (Rosenberg and Azevedo, 2019).

Evaluation of potential endophytic and rhizospheric actinobacteria for plant growth promotion and yield enhancement of mustard under field conditions

A randomized block design (RBD) with six treatments in triplicate was conducted during Rabi-season (2018–19) at PAU, Ludhiana. A total of 6 treatments included, viz. T₁ (100% RDN+MRS-15), T₂ (100% RDN+MER-33), T₃ (*Azotobacter*+75% RDN), T₄ (*Azotobacter*+100% RDN), T₅ (uninoculated+100% RDN), and T₆ (absolute control without N). Three mustard varieties (GSC-7, PC-6, PBR-357) were seed-inoculated (0.5 mL broth/g seed), coated with charcoal, and sown. Growth parameters (height, biomass) were recorded at 30, 60, 90 DAS and harvest; yield attributing parameters such as (pods/plant, seeds/pod, test weight, yield) and chlorophyll content (at flowering) were also recorded.

Effect of inoculation of potential endophytic and rhizospheric actinobacteria on quality parameters of the mustard seeds

Post-harvest, mustard seeds were used to obtain paste and extracted with acidified 80% methanol (1 g/10 mL) for 3–4 hrs. The methanol extracts were centrifuged, collected, and removed under vacuum. Total phenolic content was estimated via Folin-Ciocalteu assay (Socaci et al., 2014), with results expressed as mg GAE/g DW. DPPH radical scavenging activity was calculated using gallic acid as a standard (Tondey et al., 2022), and RSA (%) calculated as:

$$\text{RSA}[\%] = \frac{\text{Abs DPPH} - \text{AbsSample}}{\text{Abs DPPH}} \times 100$$

where

AbsDPPH is the absorbance of DPPH free radical solution in methanol

Abssample is the absorbance of DPPH free radical solution mixed with sample/standard.

Enumeration of soil microbes in soil samples

Composite soil samples at a depth of (0-15 cm) were collected at sowing and from each plot after 30, 60, 90 DAS, and at harvest. Serial dilutions were plated to estimate total aerobic bacteria, *Azotobacter*, and actinobacteria populations.

Statistical analysis

The data was subjected to analysis using (ANOVA) (SAS version 9.3, New Cary, USA) and mean separation was performed through LSD ($p \leq 0.05$) (Kaur, 2024).

Results and Discussion

Sample collection, isolation and screening of actinomycetes cultures

Actinobacteria are one of the most widely distributed groups of microorganisms in nature and serve as sources of plant growth-promoting substances. The present investigation was undertaken to isolate and screen the best-performing actinobacteria obtained from the rhizosphere and internal tissues (endosphere) of mustard plants (Supplementary Table 1). Among these, two isolates i.e MRS-15 (rhizospheric isolate) and MER-33 (root endophytic isolate) exhibited multiple functional traits important for plant growth promotion (Supplementary Table 2). These promising isolates were purified and subcultured, showing unique cultural characteristics such as spherical, entire-margined colonies with buff grey and chalky white powdery appearances (Supplementary Figure 1). Furthermore, both isolates secreted three types of hydrolytic enzymes.

Actinobacteria inhabit both the rhizosphere and endosphere of various plants. Their population is generally higher in the rhizosphere than in bulk soil, likely due to root secretions and nitrogen fixation, which create a favorable environment for microbial activity (Das et al., 2021). The isolates synthesized several enzymes known to confer resistance against seed- and soil-borne fungal pathogens (Mukhtar et al., 2017). These biotechnologically valuable microorganisms are extensively used for secondary metabolite production. Their plant growth-promoting traits were assessed through various in vitro biochemical and enzyme production assays are an essential step for selecting strains with agronomic potential before in planta evaluation (Mitra et al., 2022).

In vitro study of root surface colonization and endophytic existence of actinobacteria in mustard seeds

A healthy root system ensures better anchorage and effective acquisition of nutrients. PGPBs influence plant growth, and the beneficial effects of bacterial inoculants can be realized only if these bacteria survive in the competition with the vanguard microflora in the rhizosphere and adsorb on the root surface, followed by their movement inside the root tissues. Therefore, the PGP effect of bacterial cultures was examined for mustard seeds grown under in vitro conditions. The root length response was in the order of strain Ac2 > Ac isolates+ *Azotobacter*> Ac 1 > *Azotobacter*> untreated control.

To establish that the observed growth beneficial effect on mustard seeds were due to an association with bacteria, microscopic analysis of culture-treated mustard seedlings was performed. The seed treated with bacterial cultures exhibited better nutrient uptake as compared to untreated ones.

The optical microscopy studies revealed bacterial presence on root hairs and seedling root surfaces (Figure 1), with inoculated bacteria penetrating into root tissues. However, among the two isolates, the endophytic isolate MER-33 showed greater internal colonization, whereas MRS-15 cells aggregated on the root surface. These aspects indicated the initiation of biofilm formation on the rhizoplane. Biofilm formation enhances microbial adhesion and creates a stable rhizospheric

microenvironment, aiding nutrient assimilation and stress tolerance (Li et al., 2023). Furthermore, the cell accumulation on root surface facilitates enhanced endophytic movement. On internalization of the actinobacterial cells inside the root tissues of the host plant mediates direct nutrient acquisition, phytohormone production (e.g., IAA), and ACC deaminase activity to mitigate stress, thereby improving root architecture and nutrient use efficiency (Oloumi et al., 2023; Reddy et al., 2024). Similar colonization by endophytic *Streptomyces* has been observed in wheat and other crops, leading to improved root and shoot growth (Ezeobiora et al., 2024, Kaur et al., 2024).

Fig. 1. Stereomicrograph (panel I) and optical research microscopy (panel II) studies showing effect of endophytic actinobacteria and *Azotobacter* on root growth of mustard seedlings at 40x and 200x magnifications

Field experiment

The mean effect results showcased that among the three mustard varieties, no significant variations were recorded for the vegetative parameters, except root dry weight which was significantly lower than the other two varieties (Table 1). Among the treatments without considering other factors, maximum plant height, shoot and root fresh and dry weight were recorded for mustard seeds inoculated with endophytic MER-33 isolate at recommended full N-fertilizer dose (100% RDN).

Means within the sub-factor followed by the same letter in a column are not significantly different at $p \leq 0.05$ according to pair-wise comparison of least square means. The chlorophyll content, a key indicator of photosynthetic status and metabolism, also improved (Wang and Shi, 2024). The mustard varieties exhibited no significant variation, while inoculation of strain MER-33 resulted in significantly higher chlorophyll content (Table 1). Under adequate moisture, this increased photosynthesis supports effective translocation of photosynthate from leaves (source) to seeds (sink) (Xiong et al., 2023).

Yield attributes are the result of the vegetative development of the plant. Among the various developmental processes of the mustard plant, the formation of siliquae and seeds are a consequence of resource mobilization. Significant differences were recorded for various yield attributing traits (Table 2). Variety GSC-7 recorded the highest number of siliquae per plant, siliqua length, number of seeds per siliqua, and seed yield. However, treatments with actinobacteria or *Azotobacter* did not significantly affect the seed yield.

This non-significant effect on seed yield may be due to a variety of environmental factors and genotype \times environment interactions (Chaudhary et al., 2021), indicating the influence of N and P fertilizers (Sahay and Inam, 2015). However, yield-attributing traits were significantly improved in actinobacteria-inoculated treatments, possibly due to PGP compound secretion.

Variation in seed weight is common within and among plant species. Data on seed weight/plant showed highly significant differences among varieties and treatments (Table 2). Maximum seed

weight/plant was observed in variety GSC-7 (16.81 g) and among treatments, MRS-15 inoculation (T₁) significantly improved the seed weight/plant (Table 2), while 1000-seed weight was significantly affected by varieties (Nayak et al., 2022).

Table 1. Mean effects of varieties, treatments and days after sowing on plant growth attributes of mustard crop.

Sources	Parameters					
	Plant height (cm)	Fresh shoot weight (g)	Dry shoot weight (g)	Fresh root weight (g)	Dry root weight (g)	Chlorophyll content (mg g ⁻¹ fresh leaf tissue)
Varieties						
GSC-7	69.46a	28.31a	3.59a	3.00a	0.89a	0.42a
PC-6	73.24a	19.75a	3.59a	1.95a	0.55b	0.477a
PBR-357	79.28a	23.537a	3.86a	2.67a	0.811a	0.43a
Treatments						
T ₁	82.30a	30.37a	4.84ab	3.84a	0.91a	0.54b
T ₂	84.10a	31.96a	4.48a	3.81a	0.94a	0.63a
T ₃	74.04b	24.85b	3.56bc	2.41b	0.76ab	0.44c
T ₄	75.69b	23.77b	3.40bc	2.36b	0.71ab	0.43c
T ₅	69.79c	17.10c	2.93c	1.50c	0.60b	0.32d
T ₆	63.04c	15.15c	2.87c	1.33c	0.56b	0.28d
DAS						
30	15.26c	3.19c	0.33c	0.35c	0.06c	0.45b
60	51.75b	16.73b	2.52b	1.83b	0.45b	0.52a
90	113.82a	37.39a	5.89a	4.01a	1.21a	0.48b
120	115.15a	38.16a	5.99a	3.98a	1.27a	0.31c
ANOVA Analysis						
Variety	1766.15ns	1324.35ns	1.76ns	20.80ns	2.30*	0.05ns
Treatments	2728.15***	1659.7***	23.68***	42.43***	0.88ns	0.63***
Variety×Treatments	230.30*	62.70ns	2.09ns	2.32ns	0.30ns	0.01ns
DAS	130038.18***	15584.3***	410.36ns	171.2***	18.88***	0.47***
Variety×DAS	822.76***	348.26***	3.04ns	4.88**	0.50***	0.007ns
Treatments×DAS	278.57***	243.84***	2.77ns	6.31***	0.09ns	0.008ns
Variety×Treatment×DAS	34.67ns	17.50ns	0.58ns	0.56ns	0.07ns	0.004ns

* $p \leq 0.05$, ** $p \leq 0.01$, *** $p \leq 0.001$, ns= not significant

Table 2. Mean effects of varieties and treatments on plant yield attributes of mustard crop

Sources	No. of siliquae per plant	Siliqua length (cm)	Siliqua weight (g)	No. of seeds per siliqua	1000 seed weight (g)	Seed wt. per plant (g)	Seed yield (t/ha)
Varieties							
GSC-7	177.94a	5.86a	1.19c	16.89a	3.41b	16.81a	1.99a
PC-6	207.27a	4.99b	1.42a	15.53b	3.49b	12.63c	1.49c
PBR-357	210.16a	4.84b	1.38b	15.14b	4.40a	15.24b	1.80b
Treatments							
T ₁	229.66a	5.83a	1.49a	17.48a	4.27a	15.11a	1.79a
T ₂	227.88a	5.73b	1.51a	17.21a	4.33a	14.85a	1.76a
T ₃	209.33b	5.27c	1.32b	16.26a	3.86ab	14.82a	1.74a
T ₄	214.55b	5.39bc	1.32b	16.30ab	3.72bc	14.94a	1.77a
T ₅	185.55c	4.71d	1.19c	14.38bc	3.30cd	14.62a	1.73a
T ₆	123.77d	4.45d	1.15c	13.50c	3.11d	12.82b	1.52b
ANOVA analysis							
Variety	5721.18***	5.47***	0.27***	15.19ns	5.40***	79.96***	1.13***
Treatments	14330.10**	2.73***	0.19***	22.61**	2.20***	16.01***	0.22***
Variety×Treatments	1602.45***	0.69***	0.01**	2.24ns	0.23ns	5.96**	0.08**

* $p \leq 0.05$, ** $p \leq 0.01$, *** $p \leq 0.001$, ns= not significant

Means within the sub-factor followed by the same letter in a column are not significantly different at $p \leq 0.05$ according to pair-wise comparison of least square means.

Seed quality parameters

Mustard seeds have been considered as bioactive component of food (Grygier, 2023) due to the presence of a variety of phenolic compounds such as sinapinic acid and its derivatives (Nguyen and Nandasiri, 2024). Data on total phenolic content exhibited high significant difference among varieties and treatments (Table 3). Among varieties, significantly highest TPC was observed in seed paste of Variety PC-6 followed by varieties PBR-357 and GSC-7. Among treatments, MRS-15 inoculation exhibited the highest value for TPC (Table 3). A significant difference was found to be observed between Variety × Treatments. A likewise trend was recorded for the DPPH radical

scavenging activity with the high significant difference among varieties and treatments (Table3).

Therefore, the DPPH-RSA values serve as a rapid and sensitive method for evaluating antioxidant potential (Martinovic et al., 2020).

Table 3. Mean effects of varieties and treatments on antioxidant activity of mustard seeds

Sources	Total phenol content (TPC) (mg GAE/g DW)		DPPH Radical scavenging activity (%)
Varieties			
GSC-7	0.179b		20.994b
PC-6	0.209a		24.450a
PBR-357	0.156c		18.233c
Treatments			
T1	0.193a		22.600a
T2	0.182d		21.255d
T3	0.184c		21.533c
T4	0.188b		21.988b
T5	0.167f		19.577f
T6	0.174e		20.400e
Sources of variation	D.f.		
Variety	2	0.0128***	174.63***
Treatments	5	0.0007***	10.735***
Variety×Treatments	10	0.001***	21.194***

* $p \leq 0.05$, ** $p \leq 0.01$, *** $p \leq 0.001$, ns= not significant

Means within the sub-factor followed by the same letter in a column are not significantly different at $p \leq 0.05$ according to pair-wise comparison of least square means.

Soil microbial studies

The ANOVA results revealed significant differences in microbial counts on nutrient, Kenknight's, and Jensen's agar across all three factors (Table 4). Furthermore, dual and triple interactions showed significant variation, except for actinobacteria under the Variety × Treatments × DAS interaction.

Table 4. Mean effects of varieties, treatments and days after sowing on total microbial count of mustard crop

Factors/variables	Total bacterial count	Actinobacterial count	Free-living N-fixer count
Varieties			
GSC-7	84.08b	23.62ab	23.56a
PC-6	82.68c	23.56b	19.66c
PBR-357	87.21a	24.42a	22.24b
Treatments			
T1	88.40b	27.37a	24.84a
T2	86.33c	26.44b	24.71a
T3	85.46c	25.13c	23.11b
T4	92.84a	23.00d	20.75c
T5	76.35e	20.84e	19.40d
T6	78.57d	20.42e	18.13e
DAS			
0	34.09e	15.53e	16.38d
30	52.68d	22.25d	20.24c
60	76.53c	24.07c	21.79b
90	117.98b	27.611b	24.92a
120	142.01a	29.87a	25.77a
ANOVA Analysis			
Variety	482.38***	20.62ns	354.04***
Treatments	1713.42***	380.93***	357.78***
Variety×Treatments	222.00***	10.31***	49.32***
DAS	108617.68***	1648.00***	773.57***
Variety×DAS	263.34***	8.65**	12.44*
Treatments×DAS	236.32***	39.87***	26.63***
Variety×Treatments×DAS	5837.11***	4.03ns	17.56***

* $p \leq 0.05$, ** $p \leq 0.01$, *** $p \leq 0.001$, ns= not significant

The mean effect variations showed the highest bacterial and actinobacterial counts in variety PBR-357, while GSC-7 showcased the highest free-living N-fixer counts. Among treatments, seed inoculation with rhizospheric isolate MRS-15 notably increased actinobacterial and N-fixer counts.

In contrast, total aerobic bacteria were significantly enhanced by *Azotobacter* + 100% RDN inoculation (Table 4). Means within the sub-factor followed by the same letter in a column are not significantly different at $p \leq 0.05$ according to pair-wise comparison of least square means,

Conclusion

Therefore, this study was aimed to isolate and characterize rhizospheric (MRS-15) and endophytic (MER-33) actinobacteria from mustard plants, followed by field evaluation for their plant growth-promoting potential alongside *Azotobacter*. Both isolates formed biofilm-like aggregates on root surface and were also observed inside root hairs, confirming endophytic nature. Seed inoculation with MRS-15 and MER-33 resulted in a numerical yield increase compared to uninoculated control with 100% RDN. These findings highlight that seed inoculation with rhizospheric/endophytic actinobacteria can be a promising strategy to improve crop growth and yield.

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Author Contributions

AC, AK, APSB and VS conceived the concept, wrote and approved the manuscript.

Acknowledgements

Authors are thankful to the Head, Department of Agronomy, PAU, Ludhiana for providing the necessary infrastructural facilities for the conduct of the field experiment.

Funding

Not applicable.

Availability of data and materials

Not applicable.

Competing interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Ethics approval

Not applicable.

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Citation: Chaudhary A, Kalia A, Brar APS and Sardana V (2025) Biopriming with Beneficial Endophytic and Rhizospheric Soil Actinobacteria on Comparative Growth Promotion and Root Colonization Potentials in Mustard Crop: A Field Appraisal. *Environmental Science Archives* 4(2): 428-436.